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Factors Influencing the Academic Performance of Grade 10 Students in Science under Modular Distance Learning

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ABSTRACT

Background:

This study examined the factors affecting the academic performance of Grade 10 students in Science under modular distance learning at Sta. Isabel National High School, Division of the City of Ilagan. It focused on student profiles, perceived factors influencing performance, and their relationship to academic outcomes.

Methods:

A quantitative, descriptive-correlational design was employed. A total of 142 Grade 10 students from four sections participated. Data were gathered using a survey questionnaire adapted from validated studies and analyzed using descriptive statistics, chi-square test, ANOVA, and mean scores.

Results:

Most respondents were 16 years old or younger, male, with parents who had attained only elementary education, and whose monthly income was ₱5,000 or less. Students generally disagreed that personal conditions influenced performance, remained neutral on study and home-related aspects, but agreed on teacher- and school-related factors. Their mean Science grade was 81.45, classified as "satisfactory." Parents' educational attainment and economic status had a significant influence on performance, while other profile variables and perceived factors showed no significant relationship.

Conclusion:

The findings suggest that academic performance is more strongly shaped by socio-economic and educational backgrounds than by perceived learning factors. Recommendations include implementing remedial teaching, strengthening stakeholder collaboration, and conducting further studies to explore other variables influencing student achievement.

Keywords: academic performance in science, modular distance learning, socio-economic and educational factors, secondary education outcomes, student perceptions of learning, Philippine education system

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